

APPLYING DESIGN TOOLS FOR FULL-CULM BAMBOO

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ABSTRACT

Designers use a range of tools to conceive and visualise our built environment. Design for bamboo structures requires an understanding of the material and methods of construction in the initial design stages more so than with standardised man-made materials. This paper discusses and advocates for a mixed media of design tools which includes: concept sketching; physical model-making; computational design, specifically an algorithmic design (AD) approach; and full-scale construction; and discusses the opportunity afforded through the inclusion of an AD approach. Using methods of: self-observation; evaluation; and surveys, this paper reviews the application of this mixed media delivered through participatory action research in Panama in early 2022.

KEYWORDS

Bamboo; architectural design; model-making; design tools; computer aided design; parametric design

INTRODUCTION

Designers use a range of tools to conceive and visualise our built environment (Carpo, 2003; Di Mari & Yoo, 2012; Schilling, 2018). Two dimensional drawings work best for designs using orthogonal shapes but it is difficult to visualise forms that involve complex geometries such as hyperbolic paraboloids and hyperbolic cylinders or organic shapes. It is here another tool, physical model-making, emerges allowing one to explore geometry to find form and design. In recent decades architectural design has seen the emergence of Computer Aided Design (CAD) in the initial design stages (Aish & Bredella, 2017; Wintour, 2018), which in some cases has replaced established tools of design (Fakhry et al., 2021). As Sheil (2008) writes about contemporary practice, “*how we design has become as important as what we design*” (p. 7). This is no more than true for full-culm bamboo structures, a latent sustainable alternative to many man-made ‘conventional’ materials (Harries et al., 2012; Lou et al., 2010; UNEP, 2019), but one which requires a greater understanding of the material performance and methods of construction in the initial design stages. Therefore a greater variety of design tools should be employed to achieve wider application. This paper discusses four tools designers should use to conceive architectural design: concept sketching; physical model-making; computational design, specifically an algorithmic design (AD) approach (Burger, 2012); and full scale construction. This paper reviews literature on these tools in the design process and then reviews their synthesis through participatory action research, in a design curriculum for bamboo. This curriculum was delivered in a workshop given in early 2022 through a series of design and construction activities which took place in Panama City, Panama and the Mamóní Valley Preserve, Panama with 25 participants taking place in-person or online. AD exercises used Rhinoceros 3D (Rhino) CAD (Robert McNeel & Associates, 2020b) and Grasshopper (Robert McNeel & Associates, 2020a) algorithmic modelling software with environmental (Sadeghipour Roudsari & Pak, 2013) and live physics plug-ins (Piker, 2013). The authors both taught at or participated in these activities. This paper reviews these activities with reflections from the authors and discusses the implications of such mixed media on the process of designing with bamboo, a non-standard material with natural variabilities. The impact of these activities on students is assessed and discussed through qualitative surveys and the dialogue between participant and educators outlined in this paper deepens meaning

and relevance, and suggests opportunity in utilising these tools in architecture practice and education. The authors believe such multiple perspectives of models (physical and digital), drawings and construction is crucial to better develop awareness about bamboo in architects in bamboo growing regions.

Figure 1: Mixed media used for design exploration of the hyperbolic paraboloid form for bamboo.

DESIGN PROCESSES

Concept sketches and physical modelling

Traditional forms of architectural representation include architectural drawings and architectural models. This can vary from quick concept design sketches and blue foam models to detailed drawings and models. As Schilling (2018) defines sketching, “*Spontaneously an idea is given expression on paper*” (p. 31). Two dimensional drawings work best for designs using orthogonal shapes but it is difficult to visualise forms that involve complex geometries such as hyperbolic paraboloids and hyperbolic cylinders or organic shapes. Here another tool, physical model-making, emerges. This allows one to explore geometry to find form and design. As the role of the architect became one of the thinker and designer, and not builder, the Italian Renaissance saw the emergence of this medium, to visualise the master builder’s idea in three dimensions (Schilling, 2018). Concept sketching is often the first in this sequence of tools because lines are easier to construct on paper than physical 3D forms. However, with complex geometries, conceiving this through the medium of bamboo stick models (Figure 1a), the model can begin to be used as an efficient sketching technique to easily visualise and explore various possibilities. The modelling medium of bamboo skewers and elastic bands suggests form but also structure, and construction. Models are tools for design, representation is a simultaneous by-product. This application of models in the design process is exemplified by designers such as Antoni Gaudí and Frei Otto. Their models were used to explore new and innovative designs which facilitated the exploration of new form but could test the structural stability at the same time. This way of designing through models also produces an architecture which is inherently sustainable, efficient, minimal, and ethical (Otto & Rasch, 1995, p. 13). These models were used to, “*make the invisible measurable and the visible calculable*” (Vrachliotis, 2020).

Physical construction

Aforementioned models teach the designer much about structure and form and they start to tell of material. However, to understand the construction logic and material at the scale of the building requires building at full scale. This provides tactility, the feel of the material and the construction logic. Such a process can be termed ‘*design and build*’, as defined in Storonov (2018) as, “*the act of physically making what is designed at full scale*” (p. 1). This process can generate intuition in designers of material or construction processes. Full-scale building contacts the ground, it endures gravity. A physical object is produced, one which is at the mercy of a fourth dimension, that of time. This dimension is crucially important to experience the environmental factors which can affect the material. For a material like bamboo with low natural durability, experiencing this performance, along with the variabilities, and the eccentricities first hand is so important. Without a ‘*Ctrl+Z*’, the act of physically making teaches the importance of craft, care and responsibility (Storonov, 2018).

Algorithmic design (AD)

Until now all the tools described are analogue, and these tools can be inadequate to solve complex design problems (Lin, 2001). Eastman (1975) hypothesises the most obvious advantage of using computers in the architectural design process. They offer the “*ideal representation*” of an architectural design (digital drawings and models) producing “*infinite*” drawings, whilst centralising all design changes (Eastman, 1975, p. 46). Almost half a century later, today, computational design brings simulation and analysis into architectural design. When describing the “*ideal representation*”, Eastman (1975) is describing 3D modelling, or explicit modelling. This is the process by which each geometric object is modelled based on explicit coordinates (Burger, 2012). This can however be time-consuming when each small design change could require the remodelling of the entire model (Jabi, 2013). As (Crolla, 2017) writes, “*The assimilation of naturally variability in digital environments is not possible with conventional tools but would be a requirement if we want to use raw materials that don’t undergo extensive industrial standardisation.*” (p. 10). Algorithmic design (AD) is another paradigm in the use of computers in architecture (Wintour, 2018). AD is based in mathematical thinking in contrast to the explicit nature of Computer Aided Design (CAD) or Building Information Modelling (BIM) (Castelo-Branco et al., 2022). AD involves coding, “*explicit instructions that initiate computational procedures that generate digital forms*” (Oxman, 2017, p. 10). The advantage of such approaches is that through the manipulation of only a few variables, designers can automatically generate almost infinite possibilities (Brown & Mueller, 2018). Processes such as these are efficient and move us closer to a more optimal design solution (Jabi, 2013). The paradigm of AD provides new tools in the wider challenge to bridge the gap between the great accuracies of 3D modelling softwares and full-culm bamboo, an anisotropic material with natural variability.

The digital tools

Rhinoceros 3D (Version 7) is a three-dimensional computer graphics and computer-aided design software which uses Non-uniform rational basis splines (NURBS), to build geometry as opposed to a polygon mesh-based system (Robert McNeel & Associates, 2020b), and widely used in the architecture profession (Stavric et al., 2013). The second is Grasshopper which is a visual programming environment which runs within the Rhino platform. The main interface for algorithm design in Grasshopper is the node-based editor. Algorithms are scripted by dragging components with inputs and outputs onto a canvas (Robert McNeel & Associates, 2020a). A benefit of Grasshopper is the ability to integrate custom plug-ins (Preisinger, 2013), such as environmental (Sadeghipour Roudsari & Pak, 2013) and live physics engines (Piker, 2013). Ladybug is an open source environmental plugin for Grasshopper. Ladybug allows the designer to explore the direct relationship between site specific environmental data and the generation of graphical data outputs. This can act as inputs into the generation of geometry (Sadeghipour Roudsari & Pak, 2013). Bamboo has low natural durability and is susceptible to photodegradation through UV and visible light radiation (Liese & Tang, 2015). Such an environmental analysis tool provides a key means of ensuring the durability of bamboo in an architectural design (Naylor, 2021). In this process another tool, Galapagos, is used. This is an evolutionary solver embedded within Grasshopper. It is a heuristic solver, which are used when there are a large number of variables to consider and an exact solution cannot be found so a best fitness to the problem is sought. It is employed in order to find a best fitness outcome based on testing a variety of input variables. In the case of Naylor (2021) it is used to find the smallest roof area which will provide complete sun protection to exposed bamboo members. Another plug-in is Kangaroo which is a Live Physics engine for interactive simulation, optimization and form-finding directly within Grasshopper (Piker, 2013). An example of the use of Kangaroo to design with full-culm bamboo is seen in Crolla (2017) where it is used to produce a digital model based on previous physical models which would find its force equilibrium and produce a design geometry. On this project AD tools are crucial to accommodate in the design process, “*the variety of material inaccuracies, tolerances, and indeterminacies faced onsite*” (Crolla, 2017, p. 10). This real world information can be fed back into the design process, effectively AD provides a space for the variability of bamboo and design changes even during construction, through changes to input variables in the digital setup.

A palette of design tools – A mixed media approach

Criticisms are levelled at the mainstream use of digital tools in architectural design. Frascari (2009) observes that hand-drafted drawings are often employed as “*persuasive choreographic notations of architectural thinking*” (p. 205). He notes, that the architectural profession has embraced the use of digital information without a proper critical reflection on the conversion of the tradition of architectural drawings into the digital (Frascari, 2009, p. 205). Kwinter (1996) also critiques mainstream architectural design practice stating it operates on “*reduced matter-models designed to behave like pristine, controlled numerical milieu*” (p. 70). Rahim and Jamelle (2020) observe digital architecture has become “*detached*” from its materiality. They argue that the sophisticated use of these tools will appear in the integration of material, structure, building systems and their associated codes (p. 13). It is therefore clear that the computer as a design tool should not be a replacement for other methods. AD becomes a powerful additional tool to physical modelling, concept sketching and full scale construction. It is the belief of the authors that any design process should utilise all of these. In broader terms, given the speed that we can remodel through an AD approach, we can leave design decisions for later into the project. Scripting models which are representative of the internal design logic, rather than the explicit designed form, provide an opportunity to embrace non-conventional materials such as bamboo, and “*reattach*” materiality to the digital design. At the dawn of the use of computers in architectural design process Tom Maver noted that “*...computers were designed to complement, not replace, man. They were potentially much better than people at appraisal and analysis but people were better at synthesis and evaluation.*” (AJ, 1970, p. 472). In other words or as Yi-Luen Do (2005) phrases it, “*right tool-right time*” (p. 396). To take a phrase out of context, Algorithmic design (AD) tools are the right tool and our urgent global challenge to use bio-based construction material presents the right time.

METHODOLOGY AND AIM

To discuss the application of this mixed media approach to design, including AD, the methodology is that of participatory action research carried out through a workshop organised by the Architectural Association School of Architecture (AA) in London, in the spring of 2022. This took place in Panama (an example of a country with great potential for bamboo use) with 25 participants. The authors of this paper are both faculty and participants of this workshop. Along with John Naylor and Jörg Stamm in the authorship team, this workshop was jointly conceived and co-directed by Diego Perez Espitia and Cesar Cheng. This workshop was designed as an introduction to the material and the software, therefore most students had not used Rhino, Grasshopper, or worked with the material of bamboo before (with a list of the software students were accustomed to, discussed later in Figure 5). Similar workshops have been organised by the AA which have looked at AD software and bamboo (Kewei et al., 2022; Naylor et al., 2020). The workshop took place online and in-person. The online workshop gave us the ability to deliver all aspects of the curriculum other than physical construction if participants were unable to attend in person. The beginning of 2022 saw a spike in Covid-19 cases of the Omicron variant so the self-isolation of participants was a real possibility. This 10-day workshop in Panama is evaluated through a mixture of qualitative and quantitative evaluation methods. These include self-observation reflections and quantitative surveys. These methods together contribute to the theoretical explanations discussed in this paper. Robson (2000) describes evaluation as assessing, “*...the worth or value of something.*” (p. 3) and this is an essential reference in our reflections. To assess the value of a mixed media of design tools which includes AD. The evaluation in this study covers many aspects of the workshop preparation and the tools used. Using notes, sketches, photographs and recordings of sessions from the workshop, a self-observation was used as the method of reflecting on the experience. This evaluation focuses on the process and outcomes of the workshop and in doing this the methodology of a quantitative survey is also used with both closed and open-ended questions. These surveys were self-administered and anonymous which can help to encourage frankness and honesty (Robson, 2002).

PEDAGOGICAL LEARNINGS

Exploration of structural systems

The workshop used three structural systems as the basis of design explorations. These were a: hyperbolic paraboloid; planar truss and columns; and space frame. For this paper we will focus in more detail on the hyperbolic paraboloid.

Case study exercise – Hyperbolic paraboloid

Physical models

Building a physical model using bamboo skewers and rubber bands is a very easy and quick way to build a hyperbolic paraboloid model. Fixed length bamboo skewers are used to create a grid of 10 x 10 skewers tied at each intersection using thin rubber bands. The rubber bands are important component as it keeps the grid flexible allowing it to deform. Once the grid is tied and ready two diagonal ends of the square are pushed together and raised up, this results in the other two corners being pushed together and pushed down. The skewers slide against each other creating a twisted ruled surface. The final shape depends on the amount of pressure applied. Thin string can be tied around the model to fix the shape, or the skewers can be glued together at the intersections, once a desired shape is achieved. Various physical models were shared around the group and participants were encouraged to play with the shape to explore various possibilities. Once the hyperbolic paraboloid form has been found through the model, by pressing the form flat on a surface, the deformation of the grid is highlighted. The length and width of each section of grid is reduced in those at the centre of the grid. Once the pressure is removed from the form which is forcing this flat on a surface, the model will spring back into the hyperbolic paraboloid form. If more than one hyperbolic paraboloid is placed together it is possible to use this as one element in a larger organisation. This creates further complex forms and the physical model provides a level of tactility that is not possible when sketching or using digital tools.

Figure 2: Students integrating physical models and bamboo construction activities.

Physical construction

The hyperbolic paraboloid was constructed using Bambusa Barbatus, zip-ties, steel bolts, nuts and washers. A grid was constructed flat on the ground with zip-ties fastened at each intersection, similar to the process of the physical model. A number of participants were then tasked with deforming the grid into place raising the two opposite vertices and leaving the other two on the ground but pushing them closer together. Given this was outside this was also an opportunity for wider group work, and peer learning given everyone had the opportunity to stand with the structure and form this into place. Once in place and the form was found, holes were drilled at the strap locations and the hyperbolic paraboloid remained static. Bolts, washers and nuts were inserted at most intersections and tightened. Everyone then had an opportunity to add drill and bolt.

The algorithmic model

The experience of building regularly fed into each software exercise at every opportunity. Participants were encouraged to develop scripts which react to their 1:1 scale construction experience. Foote

(2013) describes the scenario well. Instead of *a sequence of designing then building*, “... ‘design’ and ‘build’ work in a dialectic rather than as a linear process” (p. 53). The software was taught through a series of exercises which were documented in the textbook given to students. Each exercise would teach the software as well as design awareness for bamboo. Here we are only focussing on one exercise which is that of the hyperbolic paraboloid. The way the physical model, or the 1:1 scale construction is built, informs the way we build the algorithm thanks to the flexibility of AD tools. Clarity and a clear stating of the performance criteria for the algorithmic model is required. In order to build the algorithm we also need a clear idea what information we want as an output. Will this model be used to explore form? If so, then we may not be as dogmatic in the way we construct the algorithm as this is also an opportunity to explore different algorithmic means of producing the form. Or, do we need specific information as an output? These could be material lengths, material quantities, or bolt locations. How the model will be used affects how we will build the algorithm. Identifying the performance criteria and the outputs then allows us to look at our inputs and identify the variables, constants and constraints. For example are we defining one base point and the bamboo pole lengths and then finding the achievable span of the anticlastic hyperbolic paraboloid surface? Or are we defining the span and maximum corner heights of the hyperbolic paraboloid and therefore the lengths and quantities of the bamboo poles will be calculated in the algorithm? In the case of the case study exercise (Figure 3), the constant was the length of poles to be used. The variable was the positions of the upper points. By moving these points the algorithm would deform the geometry based on the way the physical model would deform. These exercises provide the basis of the learning these tools and the parameters which inform the structural system. Examples of these variations in the algorithmic model include changing pole lengths, changing pole diameters, adding poles to the grid and applying force to the form to watch the model deform. Each of these micro-level changes will update the macro-scale. We are not modelling the form, we are finding the form (Figure 3). The algorithmic model can then be ‘Baked’ from Grasshopper into Rhino. ‘Baking’ is the process of taking the representation of the geometry from Grasshopper into NURBS geometry in Rhino. With this explicit NURBS model within the Rhino platform, we can produce drawings, export to other platforms, and produce visuals such as renders.

Figure 3: Hyperbolic paraboloid created algorithmically using the Kangaroo plug in for Grasshopper. The user interaction simulates behaviour similar to the physical model.

New possibilities for design and construction with bamboo through AD

The utility of the algorithmic model is increased if the design were to be constructed of more than one hyperbolic paraboloid. AD allows for the design and the construction of complex buildings using bamboo that were once impossible by other design media. An algorithm does not just establish relationships between individual members (poles) in the hyperbolic paraboloid, but can establish the

relationship between each hyperbolic paraboloid in a cluster. By embedding the logic of the relationship between a cluster of these forms, it is then possible to see the overall effect of manipulating one hyperbolic paraboloid on the scale of the building (Figure 4). Without AD, to rebuild each individual hyperbolic paraboloid in the cluster and then restitch them together would be time consuming, but it would be almost impossible to visualise and compute the overall form of the multiple hyperbolic paraboloids and make design decisions by any other means. The design and the realisation of such complex buildings would not be possible without the use of AD to adapt and visualise the 3D model in real-time, and obtain and analyse: the 3D data; dimensions; and corner locations. This aspect of form finding on the individual surface then proliferating and observing the effect on several is a unique aspect of AD.

Figure 4: Versions of a design to demonstrate the application of AD to construct and adapt a cluster of hyperbolic paraboloids through the manipulation of the input variables associated with only one hyperbolic paraboloid surface.

The educator experience

Many features of this workshop were influenced by another workshop which runs at the AA directed by one of the co-authors of this paper and Dr Andry Widyowijatnoko and documented in Kewei et al. (2022). The aforementioned workshop was forced to adapt in 2020 and 2021 given the Covid-19 pandemic which meant a focus to online learning and a reduction of peer interaction. Delivering a mixed media approach to designing with bamboo is then a lot more challenging in an online environment as the tactility of the model making and construction are removed and physical group work is impossible. This workshop allowed for a hybrid of these. Course directors produced a textbook prior to the workshop which allowed students to follow step by step instructions for software tutorials and online software tutorials were not recorded. This is crucially important as these sessions are designed to be interactive and private. Any fear in asking questions, or thinking out loud is only made worse if the tutor and participants feel they are being recorded. In order to facilitate this, a maximum tutor to student ratio of 1:10 is required for the software exercises. These software exercises are not just teaching the software but in many cases teaching the material of bamboo. Design decisions which are reflected in the algorithms we build as a class are influenced by the durability or buildability considerations of the material. An example of this was the day when a group built a space frame at 1:1 scale and then modelled the space frame algorithmically later that evening. The construction logic of the space frame became the internal logic of the algorithm. Participants may not know the component in Grasshopper, but they knew what the next step of this process would need to be.

Three didactic considerations when teaching software include: showing the process as a series of steps which is aided by the textbook; showing the outcome at the outset; and showing all representations (name and icon) of each component. A tool which aids the latter is *Bifocals* which is a plug in for Grasshopper. The main tool used for documentation is the platform *Miro* which is an online collaborative whiteboard platform (Miro, 2022) and *Zoom* for online video conferencing. This allowed all in person and online participants to come together. The online format is also something that will no doubt endure beyond the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic.

The participant experience

One of the co-authors participated in the workshop to learn how to use the digital tools like Rhino and Grasshopper to design structures using bamboo. They had experience in design and building with bamboo so were able to reflect on the use of different design tools and how they influence the design. The online learning environment was suitable for learning digital tools and, although the physical workshop was carried out halfway across the globe, online tools allowed for a global learning environment. The tutorial exercises were well organised and allowed for lots of questions and development. Three different exercises were explored, one of them included building a hyperbolic paraboloid. Further, three different ways of building a hyperbolic paraboloid were also explored including modelling directly in Rhino, scripting in Grasshopper allowing for a parametric design that could be changed and adapted quickly and finally using Grasshopper plugins like Ladybug and Kangaroo to further refine the design. It was surprising easily to get used to working with the software and start scripting in Grasshopper considering there was no previous experience in working with these tools.

Evaluation survey

As part of the evaluation, two self-administered online surveys were issued to participants. The first at the beginning of the workshop activities in January 2022 and then in March 2022. Surveys asked gender, age, and profession, though there was no further information asked which could be used to identify the participants, therefore results were anonymous. Surveys were also used to evaluate the impact of similar architectural design workshops conducted by the AA in Haiti (Naylor et al., 2020). Since the surveys were circulated with our student body, they have already shown an interest in the wider subject matters being evaluated. It is hoped this reduces the issues with external validity. All other questions were single answer multiple choice. Surveys were conducted by an online form in English. Even though some participants did not speak English, the simple nature of the questions we believe allowed for translations and comprehension.

RESULTS

Pre-workshop survey

There was a 68% response rate (17 responses) for the pre-workshop survey.

Existing software use

Responses for software used in both the initial design stages of a project, and for production and outputs are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Software use in the initial concept design stages and for final output. (Grasshopper was not available as an option for software use to produce drawings and final output.)

Post-workshop survey

The co-author of this paper who participated in the workshop was not included in the post-workshop survey and another student did not complete the workshop. Therefore there was 23 potential respondents to the post-workshop survey, with 44% (10 respondents) providing a response.

Useful and enjoyable aspects of the workshop in post-workshop survey

Q1 and Q2 in the post-workshop survey also asked students what aspects of the workshop were the most useful to their future needs, and most enjoyable. As shown in Figure 6, 3D modelling software which includes AD tools, scored the highest in both categories.

Figure 6: The most useful and most enjoyable aspects of the workshop.

Looking forward: Application of AD tools

A question asked, “*In your own words, can you suggest how the software could be best applied to a design process for full-culm bamboo?*” Comments were as follows. Some have been translated from Spanish to English, with edits only for spelling or grammar:

- *It could focus more in the variability of the material to make it accurate when designing with this natural material.*
- *Explore more the plug-ins and how they can help us to design with bamboo, or how to create different types of structure, not just parabolic or space frame structures.*
- *The software can be used on the process of transcribing the original idea for the project into a more accurate structural process.*
- *Hyperbolic parabola! Following an organic trace.*
- *It allows you to play with the shapes.*
- *Form finding, and ease to model complex forms, and being able also to change them easily.*
- *It would help to change the design in a quick way, with sun orientation facts.*
- *Of course, for all the reasons covered during the course: ensuring durability utilising ladybug plug-in, possibility to measure required material quantity and size, possibility to design for a specific species etc. A smooth process of testing design iterations, time-efficient and science-based decision making.*
- *The best way to design in software is by starting with a sketch and then going digital.*
- *The best way to apply the software is to take it from design to practice in the same course, this way the course would take a greater impact.*

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper firstly outlines the constituent parts of a mixed media design process for full-culm bamboo in architecture. This includes: concept sketching; physical model-making; computational design following an algorithmic design (AD) approach; and full scale prototyping. The paper also posits that the use of AD in the design process presents an opportunity to realise very complex structures, which would be impossible without 3D modelling software and AD software. This is not just in the development of the design, but the construction of such buildings would also be impossible without:

the 3D analysis of each point; the 3D data; the dimensions and corner locations. Therefore it is imperative that such tools are incorporated into the toolset of designers in bamboo growing regions of the world. This paper then reflects on the application of this mixed media approach to design through a participatory action research workshop in Panama in early 2022. The post-workshop survey showed a clear positive response to the role of computers in the design process for bamboo. Results showed both utility and enjoyment from this approach, and showed interesting future directions for the application of these tools to the design process for bamboo. An AD approach does not feature in local architectural education or practice in the respondents. We believe this gap also acts as a barrier to the wider use of bio-based non-conventional materials in local construction. Panama being an example of a country with latent bamboo resource, and a scenario mirrored throughout bamboo growing regions. The workshop in Panama illustrates both the importance of a mixed media design approach, and how the inclusion of AD in a mixed media approach to design for bamboo has the potential to enfranchise new architectural design solutions. This can now incorporate non-conventional materials such as full-culm bamboo to design challenges which until recently would once have been only achievable through the use of standardised materials.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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